

Tarahara, Parwanipur, Rampur, and Surkhet screening nurseries in 1985-87 were reviewed.

In the tests, 848 entries were evaluated for BI resistance and 644 for BB

resistance: 366 (43.2%) were resistant to BI and 61 (9.5%) to BB. Of these, 13 lines/varieties had resistance to both diseases.

Janaki, Laxmi, and KAU1727

showed high field resistance to both pathogens at all sites (see table) and might be useful parental materials. Janaki and Laxmi are released varieties. □

Resistance of upland rice varieties to pale yellow mottle virus (PYMV) disease in Sierra Leone

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PYMV disease occurs sporadically in Sierra Leone, and its incidence is increasing. Several plots in the eastern and northern provinces have had fairly high levels of infection, and the potential for considerable yield loss is high.

We tested eight released varieties and promising lines for resistance to PYMV under upland conditions at Kenema in the eastern province. Varieties were sown in 10-m² plots in a randomized complete block design with 4 replications. One set of varieties was inoculated 3 wk after seeding with sap from blended infected leaves. One set was not inoculated. All treatments received standard fertilizer application and cultural management.

ROK16 was resistant to the virus;

Response of 8 rice cultivars to inoculation with pale yellow mottle virus disease. Sierra Leone, 1983-84 wet season.

Treatment	Mean yield (t/ha)	Yield loss (%)	Mean height (cm)	Stunting (%)	Reaction ^a
ROK16	2.9		112		
ROK16 + virus	2.7	9	110	1.8	R
Lac 23	2.3		112		
Lac 23 + virus	1.1	54	106	5.4	I
ROK3	2.2		124		
ROK3 + virus	0.3	88	96	22.6	S
Tox 502-SLR	1.7		112		
Tox 502-SLR + virus	1.4	19	104	7.1	I
PN623-3	2.4		110		
PN623-3 + virus	0.3	88	70	36.4	S
IRAT8	1.6		93		
IRAT8 + virus	1.3	20	78	16	I
Tox 516-12-SLR	2.8		65		
Tox 516-12-SLR +virus	0.4	84	42	35.4	S
ROK15	2.9		109		
ROK15 + virus	0.1	97	74	32.1	S
LSD (0.05)	522		10		
CV (%)	19.3		6.4		

^aR = resistant: no infection, or faint and barely discernible leaf mottling. I = intermediate: mild leaf streaking or mottling with or without stunting. S = susceptible: evident chlorosis and leaf mottling with mild to severe stunting.

Tox 502-SLR, IRAT8, and Lac 23 gave intermediate responses (see table).

Despite its intermediate rating, Lac 23 had a significant yield reduction (54%).

PN623-3, Tox 516-12-SLR, ROK3, and ROK15, all rated as susceptible, gave significant yield reductions (84-97%).□

Development of a japonica rice variety with blast (BI) and bacterial blight (BB) resistance

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Resistances to BI and BB are not as strong in japonica rice varieties as in indica varieties. We used indica variety Tetep and japonica variety Toride 1 as BI-resistant parents and made crosses with traditional high-yielding japonica variety Aijing 23 that has BB resistance.

Japonica variety Chengte 232 derived

from Aijing 231/Ailoqing/Toride 1///Aijing 23//Nonghong 23/Tetep has been released. In artificial inoculation tests, it was resistant or moderately resistant to 13 of 14 local strong *Pyricularia oryzae* isolates and 5 *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* races (Table 1). It has 139-d duration in

Table 1. Reaction^a of Chengte 232 to 14 *P. oryzae* isolates and *S. campestris* pv. *oryzae* races. Hangzhou, China.

Variety	Reaction ^b to BI														Reaction ^b to BB					
	A1	A61	A63	B1	B15	C3	C13	C15	D1	D3	E1	E3	F1	G1	188	186	98	35	149	
Chengte 232	R	R	R	MR	R	R	MR	R	R	MR	R	S	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
Nonghu 6	S	MR	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	MR	MR	MR	R
Tetep	S	R	S	R	R	S	R	R	R	R	MR	R	R	R						
Aijing 23	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	MR	MR	R	R	R	R

^aR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible. ^bGrouping or race number based on Chinese differentials.

the late season and yields 6.8 t/ha, 8.42% more than widely grown Nonghu 6 and with better grain quality (Table 2).

Chengte 232 also is being used to generate indica/japonica rice hybrids. The F₁ of Chengte 232 (japonica)/26 Zezhao (indica) yielded 11.3 t/ha. □

Table 2. Some agronomic characteristics of Chengte 232. Hangzhou, China.

Variety	Duration (d)	Plant ht (cm)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Grains (no./panicle)	Panicle length (cm)	1000-grain wt (g)	Yield (t/ha)
Chengte 232	139	88.2	418.29	83.1	16.2	24.0	6.8
Nonghu 6	144	97.7	454.27	73.3	15.1	23.2	6.3

Insect resistance

Influence of male sterile and normal cytoplasm on expression of resistance to thrips

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Reactions to rice thrips *Stenchaetothrips biformis* among cytoplasmic male sterile and their maintainer lines seem to differ under field conditions at TNAU. We evaluated nine sets with male sterile and normal (fertile) cytoplasm for resistance in Jun 1988.

Seeds of each line were sown in 1-m-long rows, with 5 replications. Resistant check Ptb 33 and susceptible check TN1 were sown at random.

Reaction of cytoplasmic male sterile and restorer lines to thrips. Tamil Nadu, India.

Line	Damage rating ^a
V20A	1 a
V20B	1 a
Erjiunan A	9 b
Erjiunan B	9 b
IR46829A	9 b
IR46829B	1 a
IR46830A	1 a
IR46830B	9 b
IR46831A	9 b
IR46831B	1 a
IR48483A	9 b
IR48483B	1 a
MS37A	1 a
MS31B	1 a
Madhu A	9 b
Madhu B	1 a
Pragathi A	9 b
Pragathi B	9 b
Ptb 33 (resistant check)	1 a
TN1 (susceptible check)	9 b

^a Mean of 5 replications. Separation of means by DMRT at the 5% level.

Thrips incidence was severe 20 d after sowing. When all TN1 seedlings were dead, entries were rated for thrips damage on the *Standard evaluation system for rice* 1-9 scale.

Resistance to thrips differed significantly (see table). Male sterile lines IR48483A, IR46829A, IR46831A, and

Madhu A scored susceptible, but their corresponding maintainer lines scored resistant, indicating cytoplasmic-based expression of susceptibility to thrips. Male sterile lines V20A, IR46830A, MS37A, and Mangala A have high resistance to thrips that could be utilized in developing resistant hybrids. □

Genes conditioning resistance to brown planthopper (BPH)

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Although rice varieties with seven monogenic genes for resistance to BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) have been identified at IRRI, little is known about their reactions to other BPH populations. We evaluated varieties with *Bph 1*, *bph 2*, *Bph 3*, *bph 4*, *bph 5*, and *Bph 6* genes and a variety with *bph 2* + *Bph 3* genes for resistance and for fecundity, hatchability, growth, development of nymphs and increase in BPH population in Tamil Nadu, India.

IR747-B2-6 (*Bph 1*), Mudgo (*Bph 1*), ASD7 (*bph 2*), Ptb 18 (*bph 2*), Rathu Heenati (*Bph 3*), Babawee (*bph 4*), ARC10550 (*bph 5*), Swarnalata (*Bph 6*), Ptb 33 (*bph 2* + *Bph 3*), and TN1 (no resistance gene) were sown in 40-cm rows in 60- × 45- × 10-cm wooden trays. At 7 d after sowing, seedlings were thinned to 15/row and infested with 8 2d-instar nymphs/seedling. Trays were covered with fine fiberglass mesh cages. Treatments were replicated five times. When susceptible TN1 was dead, varieties were graded for damage.

To determine fecundity and hatchability, three pairs of newly

emerged brachypterous males and females were caged on 30-d-old potted plants of test varieties. Five replications were arranged in a randomized complete block design (RCBD) in a water-filled iron tray. Nymphs emerging represented the number of viable eggs produced by the females. After nymph emergence, leaf sheaths were dissected under a 20× binocular microscope and unhatched eggs counted.

To determine growth and development, 10 1st-instar nymphs were caged on 30-d-old potted plants of each test variety, with 5 replications in a RCBD. Growth was measured by the number of nymphs that became adults and the time taken. Insect growth index was calculated as the percentage of nymphs developing into adults to the mean developmental period in days.

To determine population increase, 30-d-old potted plants of each variety were infested with 4 pairs of newly emerged brachypterous males and females per pot, with 5 replications in a RCBD. Nymphs and adults were counted 20 d after infestation.

Rathu Heenati, Babawee, ARC105504 Swarnalata, and Ptb 33 rated resistant in seedbox screening (see table). Mudgo and Ptb 18 were moderately resistant. IR747-B2-6 and ASD7 were susceptible.

Fecundity and egg hatchability were significantly higher on susceptible TN1 and IR747-B2-6 and ASD7 than on